

Phenotyping of Lentil Germplasm for Ascochyta Blight Resistance in Ethiopia

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Abstract:

Lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medikus) is the most important food legume crop in the cereal-based cropping system. Ascochyta blight (*Didymella lentis*) is an emerging foliar disease affecting both quality and quantity of lentil crops. Many of the released lentil varieties from exotic sources are susceptible for Ascochyta blight. Therefore, this study was conducted to identify sources of resistance to Ascochyta blight. A total of 256 germplasm from EBI, ICARDA and EIAR Were evaluated under natural disease development at Alem Tena research site which is hot spot for Ascochyta blight in 2023/24 main cropping season. The experimental design was simple alpha lattice

and Ascochyta blight disease reaction was measured using 1-9 rating scale where 1= highly resistant and 9= highly susceptible. The analysis result revealed that there were wide ranges of variation in resistance to the disease. A total of 57 germplasm were observed resistant; 120 moderately resistant and the rest were susceptible to the disease. Ascochyta blight disease reaction was negatively highly correlated with flowering date ($r = -0.248^{**}$, $p < 0.0001$) where early maturing and late maturing germplasm were susceptible and resistant respectively. Sources of resistance to Ascochyta blight is existing in the local germplasm that can be used to develop varieties directly or through crossing and reduce the negative impacts of the disease in Ethiopia.

Keywords: *Ascochyta blight, Correlation, Lentil, Phenotyping, Resistance.*

Introduction

Lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medikus) is one of the oldest famous protein-rich food legumes. The crop is used for food animal feed and improving soil

fertility through nitrogen fixation (Frehiwot, 2009). Lentil establishes symbiotic associations with nitrogen-fixing bacteria, reducing the use of fertilizers and enhancing the productivity of cereal rotational crops. Hence, lentil and other

legume crops are an important component of farming systems, providing environmental and ecological benefits to the whole system, and are relevant for climate change mitigation (Young et al 2003 , Marques et al 2020).

Abiotic and biotic factors affect production and productivity of lentil. Along with biotic stresses rust, vascular wilt, and Ascochyta blight, caused by *Uromyces viciae fabae*, *Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. lentis*, and *Ascochyta fabae f. Sp. Lentis*, respectively, are the key fungal pathogens of lentil.

Didymella lentis can infect cultivated and wild species of lentil including *culinaris subsp. orientalis*, *L. culinaris subsp. odemensis*, *L. ervoides*, *L. lamottei*, *L. nigricans*, and *L. tomentosa* (Bayaa et al., 1994; Hernandez-Bello et al., 2006; Tullu et al 2010). The pathogen is host-specific to the *Lens* genus, being unable to cause disease symptoms on other legume crops. Ascochyta Blight attack all above ground plant parts at any growth stage under favorable conditions. The disease causes reduction in yield and seed quality.

The symptoms of the disease include lesions on leaves, petioles, stems and pods. The irregular shaped lesions on leaves, petioles and stem are tan and darker brown on pods and seeds. In severe infection, lesions can girdle the stem, leading to breakage and subsequent death of all tissues above the lesion. Affected crops under severe infection may be blighted and seed may become shriveled, reduced in size, and discolored.

The statement of the problem was production and productivity of the crop is very low (about 1.5t/ha) due to biotic (diseases and insect pests) and abiotic (water logging, drought and frost) factors. Ascochyta blight (*Didymella lentis*) is becoming a key production constraint and some of the released cultivars show some levels of resistance to the disease. There is a knowledge gaps on the diversity and mode of resistance in the improved and landraces of lentil in Ethiopia. The Objective was Phenotypic characterization

of lentil germplasm for Ascochyta blight resistance.

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

The study was conducted in 2023/24 main cropping season at Alem Tena sub centers located Northing 8.310478°, Easting 38.952605° and Altitude 1618m above sea level sub centers of Debre Zeit Agricultural research center, Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural research that are hot spot areas for lentil Ascochyta blight disease under natural condition.

Materials Used and Experimental Design

In this study a total of 256 Lentil germplasm of which 204 sourced from EBI, 40 germplasm from ICARDA and 12 released varieties from EIAR were planted at Alem Tena in 2023 main cropping season. The experimental design was simple alpha lattice in one meter length single row and thirty centimeters between rows with three replications. The experimental field of each replication was arranged in 8 blocks by 8 plots.

Artificial Infestation of Experimental Field

To overcome some of the potential problems of the natural infection and the glasshouse infection test, artificial epidemics was generated in the field. Infected debris was scattered in the experimental field that was collected from Alem Tena research station in 2021/22 cropping season. Infected debris was soaked in water for 24 hours and then sprayed on the experimental field. All the necessary data were collected. Disease severity score for the Ascochyta blight reaction on lentil germplasms were recorded according to a modified disease scoring 1-9 scale of ICARDA (Ahmad *et al.*, 1997b) as described in Table 1. The data was analyzed by using SPSS and simple descriptive statistics.

Table 1. Ascochyta Blight Disease Data Collection

Scale	Disease reaction	Description
1	Highly resistant	No lesion visible
3	Resistant	Few scattered lesions seen after careful searching

5	Moderately resistant	Lesions common and easily observed but little defoliation only in one or two patches in plot
7	Susceptible	Lesions very common and damaging
9	Highly susceptible	Lesions extensive many plants killed

Results

The score value of the evaluated varieties revealed highly variable in disease reactions (Table 2). Based on the disease score values varieties Assano, Chekol, Gudo and R-186 were showed resistant in disease reaction while varieties Adaa, Alem Tena, Alemaya, Derash and Furi were recorded moderately resistant in their disease reaction. Varieties Beredu and Jiru were showed susceptible in disease reaction score value while variety Teshale was recorded highly susceptible.

Table 2. EIAR Released Varieties Evaluated in 2023/24 Cropping Season at Alem Tena

Disease reactions	Varieties
Resistant	Assano, Chekol, Gudo, R-186
Moderately resistant	Adaa, Alem Tena, Alemaya, Derash, Furi
Susceptible	Beredu, Jiru
Highly susceptible	Teshale

Figure 1. Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research Released Varieties Disease Reaction

The evaluated ICARDA germplasm score value indicated highly variability in their disease reaction (Table 3). Germplasm ILL-71284, ILL-70156, ILL-70161 and DZ-2012-LN-0051 were recorded resistant in disease reaction score value while germplasm EC837840, ILL-117727, ILL-71281, ILL-71277, ILL-117729, ILL-117709, ILL-70110, ILL-71291, ILL-71295, ILL-70146, ILL-70162, ILL-70160, ILL-10155, ILL-71289, ILL-70148, ILL-117730, ILL-71269, ILL-70145,

FLIP-2012-58L, DZ-2012-LN-0218, DZ-2012-LN-0014 were indicated moderately resistant. From disease score value result germplasm ILL-71296, ILL-71272, ILL-70140, ILL-70143, ILL-117702, ILL-70157, ILL-117706, ILL-10986, ILL-71250 and DZ-2012-LN-0252 were showed susceptible while germplasm EC837891, ILL-70153, ILL-71287 and DZ-212-LN-0004 were recorded highly susceptible disease reaction.

Table 3. ICARDA Materials Evaluated in 2023/24 Cropping Season at Alem Tena

Disease Reaction	Germplasm
Resistant	ILL-71284, ILL-70156, ILL-70161, DZ-2012-LN-0051
Moderately resistant	EC837840, ILL-117727, ILL-71282, ILL-71281, ILL-71277, ILL-117729, ILL-117709, ILL-70110, ILL-71291, ILL-71295, ILL-70146, ILL-70162, ILL-70160, ILL-10155, ILL-71289, ILL-70148, ILL-117730, ILL-71269, ILL-70145, FLIP- 2012-58L, DZ-2012-LN-0218, DZ-2012-LN-0014
Susceptible	ILL-71296, ILL-71272, ILL-70140, ILL-70143, ILL-117702, ILL-70157, ILL-117706, ILL-10986, ILL-71250, DZ-2012-LN-0252
Highly susceptible	EC837891, ILL-70153, ILL-71287, DZ-2012-LN-0004

Figure 2. ICARDA Germplasm Disease Reaction

The evaluated EBI germplasm was revealed high variability in disease reaction (Table 4). The analysis result of EBI germplasm 242344 score value was showed highly resistant in disease

reaction while 48 resistant, 93 moderately resistant, 32 susceptible and 30 highly susceptible germplasm disease reactions were recorded.

Table 4. EBI Materials Evaluated in 2023/24 Cropping Season at Alem Tena

Disease Reaction	Germplasm accession number
Highly Resistant	242344
Resistant	241785, 207273, 233980, 231245, 231243, 242335, 211168, 242343, 207304, 238975, 238976, 207292, 207270, 207300, 211162, 244614, 235385, 211180, 242605, 230835, 211167, 243432, 231241, 213254, 207263, 207291, 233668, 237986, 28748, 215707, 215250, 230015, 211171, 211172, 242603, 28743, 230837, 207302, 232212, 232211, 235015, 241132, 233976, 233669, 228243, 229181, 235010, 233973
Moderately resistant	24219, 17994, 242354, 242355, 35418, 211169, 238980, 35421, 243445, 215709, 17993, 242361, 244604, 229182, 228809, 229184, 207287, 211161, 211163, 35415, 207277, 214932, 229178, 207258, 207307, 241784, 230657, 231242, 211176, 237504, 9236, 235384, 228242, 242364, 215710, 211186, 238969, 203462, 215488, 211174, 238274, 35412, 238990, 230521,

	207286, 21175, 229180, 243433, 242602, 214811, 213258, 28744, 28745, 35416, 211177, 230019, 230018, 230017, 207295, 207295, 244627, 207265, 29797, 35411, 211166, 241783, 244608, 19066, 244614, 233978, 244629, 243439, 231248, 237027, 35417, 235388, 235014, 230833, 235017, 244626, 243436, 244606, 243441, 243448, 244607, 221719, 238988, 208687, 244803, 235380, 231246, 233663, 244618, 244620
Susceptible	242336, 211181, 207902, 230522, 207273, 207257, 242333, 21173, 238970, 238971, 238991, 15346, 211183, 215585, 244605, 244609, 244611, 215243, 24220, 244610, 244615, 244612, 244616, 207994, 244623, 244621, 243449, 18007, 244622, 235389, 236484, 207259
Highly susceptible	229179, 207278, 242342, 230016, 227198, 207269, 211178, 15345, 207276, 207254, 238986, 238972, 211179, 207260, 244628, 230656, 238985, 238992, 243440, 241782, 28747, 28942, 35410, 207300, 243443, 244625, 233664, 237987, 207264, 207274

Figure 3. EBI Germplasm Disease Reaction

A

B

C

D

E

F

Figure 4. A -Planting, B - infected Debris scatter and soaked water spray C- flowering plant growth stage, D, E and F- Ascochyta blight infected experimental field in different view

Correlations

Ascochyta blight disease score value analysis result of lentil germplasm evaluation was showed an influence in agronomic traits (Table 5). Ascochyta blight disease reaction was showed highly negatively associated at 0.01 significant level with Flowering date ($r = -0.248^{**}$, $p < 0.0001$, $N = 768$), Biomass Yield ($r = -0.352^{**}$, $P < 0.0001$, $N = 767$) and Grain yield ($r = -0.145^{**}$, $P < 0.0001$, $N = 766$). Flowering date was associated negatively and significantly with grain yield ($r = -0.091^{*}$, $P < 0.012$, $N = 766$). Biomass yield was highly significantly associated with grain yield ($r = 0.518^{**}$, $P < 0.0001$, $N = 766$). Agronomic traits were highly affected by Ascochyta blight disease.

Table 5. Pearson Correlation

	FD	AB	BM	GY
FD	1	-.248**	-.039	-.091*
AB		1	-.352**	-.145**
BM			1	.518**
GY				1

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. FD=flowering date, AB=Ascochyta blight, BM=biomass yield, GY= grain yield

Discussion

The evaluated germplasm was revealed significant variation in flowering time. The

analysis result of flowering time ranged from 39 to 74 days. Ascochyta blight was appeared after 26 days of scattered infected debris and 24 hours infected debris-soaked water sprayed at the same time.

Leaf wetness at least 6 h required for infection and the optimal period of all three was 24-28 h. Temperature had large effects on leaf let and stem infection and subsequent development of particularly in the susceptible Eston and the moderately resistant Laird. Lesion counts indicated that the optimal temperature for infection ranged from 10 to 15 c and that very little infection occurred at 25 c (Pedersen et al., 1994).

A disease triangle describes the host plant, the pathogen and the environment. Any one of these can be altered to control a disease (Zipfel., 2014). Plant disease resistance is the ability of a plant to prevent pathogen from entering in the cuticular layer, cell walls and stomata guard cells. Once pathogens have overcome these barriers, plant receptors initiate signaling pathways to create molecules to compete against the foreign molecules. The path ways are influenced and triggered by genes within the host plant and can manipulated by genetic breeding to create resistant varieties (Decreux et al., 2005).

Develop symptoms in response to pathogen attack that could be visualized and quantified to assess the severity of disease, and these responses was differed between germplasm in

relationships of symptoms and progress rate. The variation was precisely quantified, and could be correlated with changes at cellular and gene expression levels and could lead to gene identification for improving *Ascochyta* blight disease resistance from the germplasm.

Ascochyta blight infection and fundamental host plant resistance mechanism of AB pathogens penetrates the first layer of the plant defense system conferred by host cuticle and epidermal cells using penetration pegs (Decreux et al., 2005). The pathogen spores land on the surface of the host and germinate to form germ tubes that bear appressoria and penetration pegs. The pathogens secrete carbohydrate active enzymes, to degrade cellulose, hemicellulose, and chitin and spread infection inside host plant cells (Zhang, 2012). After penetration the pathogen establishes organic relationships with the host cell. In retaliation to pathogen attack, the host generates oxidative stress to kill or damage the pathogen hyphae.

AB pathogens establish successful infection after overcome the host's pattern triggered immunity (PTI) and effectors triggered immunity (ETI) mediated defense mechanisms. In response to AB attack, the host plant recruits PTI, or basal defense mechanism (Zipfel C. and Robatzek S., 2010) and ETI (Cui et al., 2015). Through PTI, the host plant recognizes microbial elicitors/plant associated molecular pattern (PAMPs) using pattern recognition receptors embedded in the cell membrane, activating the plant defense mechanism (Boller T. and He, S.Y. 2009). After perceiving the PAMP signal, the pattern recognition receptors of receptor-like protein kinases (Wan et al 2008) and brassinosteroid insensitive associated kinase (Chinchilla et al 2007) induce reactive oxygen species that enhance the influx of cytosolic Ca²⁺ and trigger mitogen-activated protein kinase signal cascades (Nakagami et al 2005). Consequently, various host phytohormones like jasmonate, ethylene, ABA are induced to activate various downstream target transcription factors (TFs), and switch on downstream transcriptionally active genes encoding defense related proteins of pathogenesis-related proteins, osmotins providing plant protection

against the invading AB pathogens (Yuan et al 2021). Through ETI defense mediated by host disease resistance(R) gene(s) the effector molecules secreted by the AB pathogen are recognized by host plasma membrane-based nucleotide-binding/leucine-rich repeat (NLR) receptors with coiled-coil (CC) domain NLRs (CNL) and HeLo-domain RNLs that form Ca²⁺-permeable channels (Parker et al 2022). The consequent enhanced influx of cytosolic Ca²⁺ renders enhanced pattern recognition receptor immunity mediating pathogen and host cell death due to a hypersensitive response.

Lentil AB disease resistance genes encode proteins that detect pathogens. Resistance genes have been used in resistance breeding programs for many years with varying gradations of achievement. Resistance genes contain the information for the production of a protein that makes an antibiotic in effective and hence confers resistance against an antibiotic to a pathogen. Germplasm was showed a range of reaction from fully susceptible to immune for the pathogens of which they were a host. Resistance Germplasm could be one of the most effective, inexpensive and environmentally sound means for managing *Ascochyta* blight disease. Resistance germplasm was restricted the growth and development of a pathogen and the damage it caused but susceptible germplasm was showed more severe symptoms or damaged than highly resistance.

Lentil disease resistance protects from pathogens by pre-formed structures and chemicals, and infection induced responses of the immune system. Relative to a susceptible germplasm, disease resistance is the reduction of pathogen growth on or in the plant leads a reduction of disease.

Although obvious qualitative differences in disease resistance were observed when lentil germplasm under field condition were compared allowing classification as resistant or susceptible after infection by the pathogen strain in similar environment. A progression of quantitative differences in disease resistance was more characteristically observed between lentil germplasm. The evaluated germplasm analysis

result was showed that 1 highly resistant, 56 resistant, 120 moderately resistant and the others were observed susceptible disease reaction. Lentil germplasm field evaluation is done and resistant, susceptible and highly susceptible result is observed at Alem Tena substation under Debre Zeit Agricultural research center, Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (Zewdie and Gemechu, 2020) Lentil has a substantial amount of genetic variability for AB disease resistance. Cultivated species confer AB disease resistance in lentil, with Indian head, Laird, ILL5588, and ILL5684 (Tay T. and Slinkard A.E 1989). AB disease resistance sources in lentil, focus on identification of germplasm strategy assisted in identifying 87 landraces, like IC207, as AB disease resistant after assessing 4567 accessions against *Ascochyta lentis* FT13037 isolate in the field. Similar to the study accessions are promising sources of AB disease resistance in lentil (Dadu et al., 2021). Accessions W63241 and W63261 (*L. orientalis*), W63192 (*L. ervoides*), W63222 (*L. odemensis*); and ILWL235 (*L. odemensis*) Ye et al 2003) have been used to determine the genetics of AB disease resistance and hence could be used as donor parents for developing AB disease resistant of lentil cultivars.

Germplasm consistently resists certain pathogens but cease resistance to others; resistance could be usually specific to certain pathogen species or pathogen strains.

Suitable and effective screening techniques could be the major component of the breeding programs for disease resistance. A complete understanding of resistance type, pathogenicity, virulence pattern and the effective breeding strategy is required to obtain desirable results. Successful plant breeding depends on accessible genetic variability in the germplasm and its sustainable exploitation (Upadhyaya et al., 2011). Therefore, it could be imperative to have extensive knowledge of lentil germplasm that are potential sources of disease resistance.

Genotyping differences for AB disease resistance reaction were observed on evaluated materials from highly resistant to highly susceptible germplasm. Disease symptoms on

different accessions ranges from small flecks or resistant to extensive lesions on both leaves and stems with death of some plants highly susceptible (Nasir and Bretag,1998).

Genetic resistance has been commonly used to control plant diseases. Success of a breeding program aiming at incorporating disease resistance depends on the availability of diverse sources of resistance and could be greatly enhanced by knowledge of genetic control, evolutionary potential of the pathogen, appropriate choice of breeding methods and more importantly strong selection tools.

Quantitative resistance is dependent on several minor-effect genes with an additive effect on the phenotype located in different loci (Poland and Rutkoski, 2016). Quantitative resistance traits can be said to be complex traits. In terms of breeding, quantitative resistance is considered to be more durable. Due to many genes involved in different loci, the inheritance of a quantitative resistance trait is not dependent on one gene like in the case of a qualitative resistance trait. Considering quantitative resistance traits across populations is possible, as they may have a cross-population and even interspecies application (Poland and Rutkoski, 2016).

Monocultures of susceptible varieties enhance agroecosystem vulnerability and would require intense and costly disease management strategies in the event of severe epidemics. Farmers reliance on repeated chemical sprays raised environmental and food safety concerns and can potentially lead to emergence of new chemical resistance pathogen strains. Utilization of host disease resistance is considered the most sustainable approach to protect plants against various pathogens (Khan and Korban 2022).

Conclusion

Phenotyping characterization of lentil germplasm against *Ascochyta* blight disease resistant revealed genetic variations under natural hot spot area in the field conditions combined with scattering of infected debris and sprayed 24 hours infected debris-soaked water on the experimental field. The evaluation

identified highly resistant, resistant, moderately resistant and susceptible germplasm in disease reaction using 1-9 ICARDA disease rating scale. Early maturing germplasm was revealed susceptible in *Ascochyta* blight disease reaction while late maturing was observed resistance.

Future studies should be directed to screen large number of available lentil germplasm for *Ascochyta* blight disease resistance in the field-based screening and artificial screening in phytotron or high throughput phenotyping facility. Proper germplasm screening should be an important step towards for the developing of disease resistance cultivars. Phenotyping and genotypic association of targeted trait should be done to enhance the breeding program in genetic variability of resistant sources for lentil *Ascochyta* blight disease.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interests.

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